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DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RESOURCES

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D3.3
Dissemination and communication resources

WP3. Dissemination, Communication and Education

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report on Deliverable D3.3 describes the dissemination, communication and education promotional and training resources and materials generated up to date. The document firstly describes the promotional materials including mugs, slides templates, posters, roll-ups, factsheets, leaflets, infographics, promotional videos, podcasts, and newsletters that have been released throughout the past months. Then, it describes the different press releases that have been published so far. Finally, it includes the agenda of the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop and SUNERGY kick-off event and the list of participants who attended these milestone events. The document will be updated at the end of the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) with the final materials.

So far, the CSA has reached a large number of supporters and followers, especially within the scientific community, both from academic and industrial sectors. The main dissemination and communication tools planned have all been deployed with a strong commitment and involvement of the consortium partners. The current supporting community has been very active. However, further reaching of the general public and policy makers remains as one of the main ongoing challenges.

The release of promotional and training resources – particularly, supporting audiovisual materials, such as videos, infographics, slides, etc. – as well as the organization of the SUNRISE Stakeholder face-to-face workshop have all been crucial to fulfill the conditions required for the success of the dissemination and communication strategy, complying with three conditions: (1) Continuous operation of communication tools; (2) Up to date and adapted content to address the different target audiences; and (3) Active engagement at the European and member states level.

The upcoming merging of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X initiatives will provide a great opportunity to reach a much larger community. Consequently, the merger will involve changes in the dissemination and communication actions as the new image and brand position are being established. Moreover, the future goals for the newly established joint large-scale research initiative will have to be agreed by both CSA consortia.

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1. PURPOSE OF THE SUNRISE PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Following the Dissemination and Communication plan, firstly drafted at the proposal stage and updated through the development of the CSA, see D3.1, several promotional materials have been produced to facilitate the targeted dissemination, communication and education goals.

The promotional materials include templates for the presentation of the initiative and its outcomes: slides, posters as well as flyers, infographics, newsletters and videos. In addition, a list of press clippings, including replication of press releases and media interviews to project partners is also included, as well as the public agenda and registration list of both the SUNRISE Stakeholders Workshop organised in Brussels in June 2019 as one of the EUSEW (European Sustainable Energy Week) Energy Days and the SUNERGY kick-off event jointly organised with ENERGY-X as the closing event for both CSA initiatives.

2. LIST OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

2.1. Mugs

At the beginning of the CSA, SUNRISE mugs were generated as promotional material. The mugs have been shared among partners and speakers at SUNRISE meetings and other gatherings attended by SUNRISE members. Besides, some SUNRISE mugs have been used as “prizes” for contributors in SUNRISE fair stands and contests, they were sent to participants that voted in the second leg of the poll for the SUNRISE logo and were given away to participants answering a survey about the SUNRISE App at the EUSEW stand (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. SUNRISE mugs.

2.2. Slides Templates

SUNRISE partners have been very engaged and active introducing the initiative at the numerous conferences, workshops and meetings in which they have participated. To this end, a series of standard slides for presentations were created including a general presentation layout and blank slides. For events at which only one slide or very few ones could be shown, a one-slide summary or a three-slide presentation were also made available to the consortium partners in order to get a snapshot of SUNRISE initiative. These are accessible for SUNRISE partners from the PLAZA intranet created for the project partners (see Figs 2-4).

Figure 2. Examples of slide templates

Figure 3. General summary one-slide template

Figure 4. General summary three-slide template

2.3. Posters

A poster titled ‘SUNRISE: Solar energy for a circular economy’ was created to showcase the project at various events (see Fig. 5). It is also available to all the partners from the PLAZA intranet of the project’s website. Notably, the SUNRISE poster won the ‘Best Poster Award’ at the 17th International Conference on Carbon Dioxide Utilization (ICCDU), which took place on June 23 – 27 2019, in Aachen, Germany (<https://sunriseaction.com/sunrise-poster-wins-best-poster-award-iccd/>).

Figure 5. SUNRISE poster awarded at ICCDU, 2019.

The poster has been presented at different events, *e.g.* *RSC Artificial Photosynthesis Faraday Discussion*, Cambridge, 25-28 March 2019 (<https://sunriseaction.com/event/rsc-artificial-photosynthesis-faraday-discussion/>), *SUNRISE POLAND Stakeholder Workshop*, Warsaw, 5-6 June 2019 (<http://sunriseaction.com/event/sunrise-poland-stakeholder-workshop/>) and *Bringing value to CO₂*, Madrid, October 2-3, 2019 (<https://sunriseaction.com/event/aportando-valor-al-co2/>). Pictures below:

Figure 6. Pictures of SUNRISE poster exhibited at the *RSC Artificial Photosynthesis Faraday Discussion* and at *Bringing value to CO₂*, respectively

2.4. Roll-ups

Two different roll-ups were designed to be used at the consortium meetings, workshops, industrial fairs, congresses, etc. as branding materials. While the main one contains the project’s logo, title, consortium members, social media channels and a call to action, the second one explains the artificial photosynthesis process and it has been designed to be displayed at fairs and outreach events. These are also available at the PLAZA intranet. See pictures below:

Figure 7. SUNRISE roll-ups.

D3.3. Dissemination and communication resources

Both roll-ups have been used at all the different SUNRISE national stakeholder workshops, as well as at the initiative's consortium meetings, fairs, and other gatherings attended by SUNRISE members, e.g. during a visit of the SUNRISE consortium partner Artur Braun (Empa) at the University of Pretoria (<https://sunriseaction.com/sunrise-on-the-road-towards-circular-secular-economy-south-africa/>). Example pictures are included below:

Figure 8. Pictures of SUNRISE roll-ups at the Big Challenge Science Festival in Trondheim, and at the SUNRISE consortium meeting in May 2019 in Bologna (Italy), respectively

Figure 9. Pictures of SUNRISE roll-up at the Stakeholder Workshop in Brussels, and at the University of Pretoria, respectively

The second roll-up that explains the artificial photosynthesis process was also used in a poster format at the COP25 on December 5-7, 2019. See the picture below:

Figure 10. SUNRISE roll-up in poster format at the COP25.

Besides these roll-ups, two beach flags were also developed for the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop, held in June 2019 in Brussels, to indicate the venue direction to the participants.

Figure 11. One of the two SUNRISE beach flags at the venue entrance of the Stakeholder Workshop

2.5. Factsheet, leaflet and infographics

A factsheet and a leaflet containing the project's logo, title, consortium members, social media channels and a call to action were developed to be used at the consortium meetings, workshops, industrial fairs, congresses, etc. as branding materials. They are also available on the SUNRISE website (<https://sunriseaction.com/resources/>) and in the PLAZA intranet to be downloaded and printed by the partners. See pictures below:

GOALS OF THE FUTURE RESEARCH INITIATIVE

SUNRISE is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) candidate to develop a European large-scale research initiative, based on 3 main goals:

- 1 The provision of sustainable fuels from renewable energy (solar fuels)
- 2 The synthesis of commodity chemicals from renewable energy (solar chemicals)
- 3 The development of efficient methods to recycle CO₂ from the atmosphere

Be a change maker & Join our community!

SUNRISE

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Reach us at: contact@sunriseaction.eu

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Twitter: @sunriseaction | Facebook: @sunriseaction

RG: SUNRISE - Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

IN: SUNRISE - Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Towards a sustainable alternative to the fossil-based, energy-intensive production of fuels and base chemicals

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336

www.sunriseaction.eu

Figure 12. SUNRISE leaflet

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

SUNRISE relies on artificial photosynthesis as a sustainable alternative to the fossil-based, energy-intensive production of fuels and base chemicals. The energy required will be provided by sunlight and the raw materials will be molecules abundantly available in the atmosphere, such as water, carbon dioxide, oxygen and nitrogen (H₂O, CO₂, O₂ and N₂).

Recent IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) reports point out the necessity to reduce carbon dioxide emissions to achieve negative emissions in the second half of the 21st century. Technologies allowing the transition to a low- and negative-emission society are not available yet and significant research and development efforts are crucially needed.

Storing surplus electric energy efficiently and reliably remains one of today's top challenges. Storage processes converting electricity and solar energy into fuel and chemicals, much more efficient than biomass production, are highly desirable.

For the transport and heating sector, fossil fuels are an unmatched energy source, coming along with a huge, existing infrastructure. Also the chemical industry, supplying a variety of indispensable bulk chemicals for every day life, is completely dependent on fossil-based raw materials such as crude oil.

Generating alternative fuels and chemical raw materials from renewable energy sources represents a real game changer.

A replacement of fossil-based raw materials and a modernisation of the production processes are crucial for Europe's vision of a zero-emission society and the global competitiveness of its industry.

Solar energy

SUNRISE Disruptive Technologies

Solar fuels
Solar chemicals

- Methane
- Hydrogen
- Alcohols
- Fertilisers
- Base chemicals

Closed Carbon Cycle

H₂O, CO₂, O₂, N₂

FUTURE RESEARCH INITIATIVE: SUSTAINABLE FUELS & CHEMICALS VIA A CIRCULAR APPROACH

IN THE SHORT TERM, SUNRISE aims at providing value chemicals using renewable electricity sources and waste CO₂ from industrial processes as raw material for the circular production of chemicals and fuels.

IN THE LONG TERM, Final targets are sustainable high-value products produced by technologies going beyond the natural photosynthesis process, with higher efficiency and a wider selection of target molecules.

THE KEY ENABLERS. Information technology and bottom-up engineering of new advanced materials will enhance this ambitious paradigm shift. Information technology will enable optimized production processes, with savings of energy and feedstocks. New advanced materials will allow cost-competitive, efficient and durable solutions across a number of renewable energy technologies.

Paradigmatic change of the economic system accelerated by SUNRISE

- Unsustainable
- Limited
- Environmental impact
- Geopolitical dependencies

- Sustainable
- Unlimited
- Environmentally friendly
- Local/regional approaches

Market readiness level

Solar fuels and chemicals: timescale

We target a sustainable CO₂ cycle, where the concentration in the atmosphere is decreased and then maintained at a level compatible with climate stability, with sustainable use of natural resources and land. The research and innovation programme will allow European economies to convert up to 1000-2500 ton atmospheric CO₂ per hectare per year, depending on the latitude. We will deliver disruptive technologies, absorbing 90% of light and storing 80% in to products. The technology development will take into account key constraints such as the EROI (Energy Return On Investment) and availability and durability of critical materials.

www.sunriseaction.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336

Figure 13. SUNRISE factsheet

Figure 14. SUNRISE leaflets at the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop

In September 2019, a collection of three infographics was developed to promote a better understanding of the concept of circular economy as opposed to the linear economy. See the pictures below:

Figure 15. SUNRISE infographics on the circular economy

These illustrations have been shared at fairs and meetings ever since. Besides, they are also available on the SUNRISE website to be downloaded and printed (<https://sunriseaction.com/sunrise-infographics-breaking-down-circular-economy/>).

Figure 16. SUNRISE infographics on the circular economy at the Maker Faire Barcelona 2019

2.6. Videos and podcasts

The project has produced a general video to promote the initiative's objectives. It has been also used to promote the SUNRISE initiative at various events and meetings. The video was released in June 2019 and had its premiere at the EuroNanoForum 2019 conference on June 12-14 in Bucharest where it was presented during the invited talk of SUNRISE partner Joanna Kargul. To date, the promo film has reached more than 1,000 views on SUNRISE YouTube channel (<https://youtu.be/TTI98tcIyRw>) and 1,200 views on the LinkedIn page. A direct link is also available on the SUNRISE website (both landing and resources' pages).

Figure 18. SUNRISE video playing at the SUNRISE stand in the EUSEW 2019

The video has been translated to several languages to facilitate its sharing within local communities.

- Spanish (<https://youtu.be/mD3yko0s70I>),
- Italian (<https://youtu.be/rUQ0QimTCz8>),
- French (<https://youtu.be/D1PXgzDdYEk>),
- Polish (<https://youtu.be/6DqxNKB14GY>),
- German (<https://youtu.be/TTI98tcIyRw>).

Figure 19. Frames of SUNRISE official video in Spanish, Italian, French, Polish and German, respectively

Besides this video, SUNRISE has released other videos, which include:

- Two Facebook live interviews with the SUNRISE Deputy Coordinator, Hervé Bercegol (CEA) on the occasion of the International Day of Light (<https://www.facebook.com/sunriseaction/videos/424227408130413/>), and with SUNRISE partner Antonín Vlček (J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry) on the occasion of SUNRISE consortium meeting in October 2019 in Brussels (<https://www.facebook.com/sunriseaction/videos/3140475342660490/>).

Figure 20. Facebook live interviews with Hervé Bercegol and Antonín Vlček, respectively

- Four promotional videos were produced for the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop (<https://twitter.com/sunriseaction/status/1140242756067106817>), the release of the SUNRISE technological roadmap (<https://twitter.com/sunriseaction/status/1195015920403525632>), the participation of the project at the COP25 (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHQyKE7Wxo0>) and the final project event, together with ENERGY-X that was also the presentation of the joint initiative SUNERGY (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u9V-SNqazO4>).

Figure 21. Frames of promotional teasers for: SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop, SUNRISE technological roadmap, participation at the COP25 and SUNRISE & ENERGY-X final joint event, SUNERGY kick-off.

- Four video interviews with SUNRISE partners Nicola Armaroli (CNR), Helene Lepaumier (ENGIE), Huub de Groot (Leiden University) and Katrin Mueller (Siemens) on the circular economy (<https://youtu.be/iIxUxxlPgml>), renewable fuels (<https://youtu.be/wXEB3O16zcQ>), breaking down the artificial photosynthesis (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hyXG3m3bWlQ>) and solar energy for a carbon-neutral society (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_n_1-iEO-Sk), respectively.

Figure 22. Frames of SUNRISE video interviews with Nicola Armaroli, Helene Lepaumier, Huub de Groot and Katrin Mueller.

D3.3. Dissemination and communication resources

Given that some SUNRISE partners have been invited to radio interviews, podcasts out of these interviews have been generated and are also available on the SUNRISE YouTube channel. So far, there are three podcasts with SUNRISE partners Victor de la Peña (IMDEA Energy) (<https://youtu.be/SwW6-uM5daY>, Spanish), Nicola Armaroli (CNR) (https://youtu.be/rx-Wx2Rn_W0, Italian), Julio Lloret and Elisabet Romero (ICIQ) (<https://youtu.be/fcVx5VB71os>, Spanish and Catalan) on the artificial photosynthesis.

Other external videos related to the artificial photosynthesis have been posted on the project's website (<https://sunriseaction.com/videos/>) and saved on the SUNRISE YouTube channel as a playlist (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLW3cKW0AeHgZPlsGqkfQkRoSyIPYss06->) to attract the lay public's attention to the topic.

A wrap-up video presenting views of different SUNRISE partners on the first year of the CSA project was released at the beginning of February, for the final SUNRISE consortium meeting.

Figure 23. Frame of the Bye, bye SUNRISE video.

2.7. Newsletters

The project has produced four public newsletters to facilitate quick access to all SUNRISE stakeholders about the major news and outcomes of the project. The first public newsletter was sent on 2 July 2019, the second one on 7 October 2019, the third one on 14 January 2020 and the final one was released on 9 March 2019. They are available on the 'resources' page of SUNRISE webpage (<https://sunriseaction.com/resources/>). Free subscription is available on the webpage – homepage and 'support us' page –, and on the SUNRISE Facebook page.

Figure 24. SUNRISE first newsletter

The final newsletter contains the year wrap-up in the form of a digital story, to summarize the main important actions throughout the year of the CSA.

Figure 25. Frames of the year wrap-up included in the last SUNRISE newsletter.

3. COOPERATION WITH ENERGY-X, JOINT MATERIALS

3.1. SUNERGY name, logo and visual identity

Since the announcement of the joint cooperation of ENERGY-X and SUNRISE in August 2019 at EuropaCat, both communication teams from SUNRISE and ENERGY-X have worked together in order to:

- increase the synergy between both communities;
- unify the message and the vision of the joint initiative; and
- create the SUNERGY visual identity.

In a first moment, the joint communication team launched a public poll for making the final decision of the name of the joint initiative, choosing from the two final options, as previously decided in an internal poll within both consortia: SUN2X or SUNERGY. After a week of a tight race between the two proposed acronyms, the winning name was SUNERGY. This option counted with the support of 55% of the votes, against the 45% that voted SUN2X (<https://sunriseaction.com/announcing-the-winning-name-for-energy-x-and-sunrise-upcoming-joint-initiative-sun-ergy/>).

Figure 26. Results of the public poll for choosing the joint initiative name

After the definition of the name of the joint initiative, the joint ENERGY-X and communication teams worked on the visual identity of SUNERGY. In total, nine different propositions were evaluated by the SUNERGY boards and the final decision is presented below:

Figure 27. Round and horizontal versions of the SUNERGY logo.

One of the joint actions of both initiatives was also related with this final joint event: the **SUNERGY photo contest** (<https://sunriseaction.com/sun-ergy-photo-contest/>). The idea of the contest has evolved from a first idea regarding a slam video contest, which at the end was simplified for having a better and quicker reaction to become a photo contest addressed to young researchers. The contest was launched at the end of December, offering to participants the opportunity to show their research using a freestyle picture along with an abstract. The received entries were voted in the new SUNERGY Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/sunergy.eu/>) and the three most “liked” were evaluated by a SUNERGY panel, which chose the

Figure 29. Frame of the SUNERGY kick-off event video.

3.3. SUNERGY 2 pager and manifesto

Among the different materials developed jointly by SUNRISE and ENERGY-X there are the SUNERGY two-pager and a manifesto. The two-pager serves as a factsheet that draws to a great extent on the joint partnership proposal, summing up the goals, impact and means to be used by the upcoming initiative towards a climate-neutral EU by 2050.

Instead, the scope of the joint manifesto is to address scientists, industry, policymakers and citizens alike, and to be used both in policy and broader dissemination actions.

Figure 30. First page of the SUNERGY two-pager and the cover page of the manifesto

4. PRESS CLIPPINGS

4.1. Press releases

Four press releases have been published and are available for downloading from the webpage (<https://sunriseaction.com/press-releases/>)

- 1st Press release: 1 February 2019, to announce the CSA project

PRESS RELEASE

Brussels, 1st February, 2019

SUNRISE, a preparatory action towards a European large scale research initiative

- The European Project SUNRISE, “Solar energy for a circular economy”, has been selected as one of the six Coordination and Support Actions (CSA) within the Horizon 2020 programme. Funded with €1M, it will last one year (starting in spring 2019), setting the basis for a European large scale research project.
- The SUNRISE Vision is a radical and ambitious scientific and technological approach for solar energy conversion and storage to provide a sustainable alternative to fossil-based, energy-intensive production of fuels and base chemicals. This is fully aligned with the recently released European Commission long-term strategy for a [climate neutral Europe by 2050](#).
- SUNRISE joins together stakeholders from academia, industry, policy and society, including NGOs and global players in the energy, chemicals and automotive sectors, to develop the S&T roadmap of a large research initiative in the Energy, Environment and Climate Change area.

Six CSA projects have been selected for the 2018 call “FETFLAG-01-2018” within one of the three main research areas proposed: Information and communication technology (ICT) and Connected Society; Health and Life Sciences; and Energy, Environment and Climate Change. These actions aim at preparing new European large scale research initiatives to be potentially supported in the next European research and innovation framework programme, Horizon Europe. The selected proposals are urged to set the basis for large visionary, science-driven, long-term research projects focused on addressing the major European societal challenges and turning scientific advances into concrete innovation opportunities, growth and jobs.

SUNRISE, as part of the Energy, Environment and Climate Change area, gathers players from academia, industry, policy-making and society to prepare a strategic long-term research roadmap and a consolidated vision of a future large research project. SUNRISE aims at providing a sustainable alternative to the fossil-based, energy-intensive production of fuels and chemicals, based on solar energy conversion and widely available feedstock (CO₂, H₂O, N₂). A sustainable CO₂ cycle, which leads to an atmospheric CO₂ concentration decrease and stabilisation at a level compatible with climate stability, is the main target behind this approach, which also aims for a sustainable use of land and natural resources to implement a circular economy.

“SUNRISE goal is to change the way fuels are produced, and provide chemicals and much more for the circular economy with very high yield directly from abundant solar energy and atmospheric gases. In the foreseeable future, a portfolio of SUNRISE technologies will fuel carbon neutral industries in smart liveable cities that go well beyond current imagination. We will provide seasonal energy storage in a zero waste society while reducing CO₂ emissions” – Prof. Huub de Groot, SUNRISE coordinator.

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SUNRISE Solar energy for a circular economy

SUNRISE is coordinated by Prof. Huub de Groot from Leiden University (the Netherlands) and brings together a multidisciplinary consortium of 20 partners from 13 European countries. The SUNRISE consortium includes: seven universities (Leiden University, University of Uppsala, Imperial College London, University of Turku, University of Warsaw, Norwegian University of Science and Technology and University of Louvain); eight research centres (French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (CEA), Italian National Research Council (CNR), Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (Empa), IMDEA Energy Institute, Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia); two European associations (European Energy Research Alliance, EERA; Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative, EMIRI); and three companies (Siemens AG, Johnson Matthey and ENGIE).

On November 15th 2018, the consortium organised a SUNRISE meeting gathering around 90 members of the SUNRISE community in Brussels. Fruitful discussions on the project's vision, mission and strategy were held by project partners and supporters (the detailed agenda and copies of the presentations are available for download under www.sunriseaction.eu). This has been the first step for building a strong and actively growing "SUNRISE ecosystem", which will be essential to achieve the ambitious objectives of a future long-term research project. Currently, the SUNRISE initiative already counts with the support of more than 150 institutions worldwide, including academic centres, industrial companies, strategic networks, funding bodies, ministries and NGOs.

At the end of the CSA, the SUNRISE community will release a blueprint for the implementation of the SUNRISE large scale initiative, including a description of the short to long-term objectives, resources needed and the criteria to be followed for being an open, inclusive and cross-disciplinary effort following the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles.

SUNRISE will facilitate the transition to a circular economy and a carbon neutral society. The technologies to be developed as part of a large research initiative will transform carbon dioxide, water, nitrogen and oxygen feedstock into fuels and chemicals using sunlight. Electrochemical conversion using renewable power in combination with electrolysers will be complemented with integrated artificial photosynthetic systems and biohybrid approaches for the direct conversion of sunlight into chemical compounds.

Media contacts

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- 2nd Press release: 21 June 2019, to summarize the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop during the EUSEW

SUNRISE - Press release

SUNRISE's first big event takes place during the EU Sustainability Energy Week

Brussels, June 21, 2019

Over 170 SUNRISE's stakeholders gathered on June 17-18 at the Academy Palace of Brussels, in connection with the EU Sustainable Energy Week, as one of the Energy Days. Renewable energy experts from Academia, Industry and Policy addressed the current state of the initiative and its priority research directions.

Discussions showed how solar conversion by artificial photosynthesis for fuel and chemicals could contribute to climate neutrality and negative emissions by developing an ambitious yet realistic roadmap, and aligning action in research, innovation and industry policy – while ensuring the involvement of all the stakeholders. This was SUNRISE's first big event since it became a Coordinated and Support Action (CSA) in March 2019.

SUNRISE's vision and governance

During the first day, speakers shared their latest advances and their fit into SUNRISE's vision towards a clean energy future. Researchers like Jens Nørskov or Marcella Bonchio pointed out the importance of real collaboration between Industry and Academia, as well as the need of financial support. "It is a Sputnik moment for Europe, we need to approach politicians and convince them that Europe can lead the way of the renewable sector," stressed Jens Nørskov, Professor at the Technical University of Denmark.

Policy makers of the European Commission, Member States, Industry and funding bodies representatives also joined the meeting by taking part in a panel debate. The discussion tackled the governance and funding steps of large-scale research initiatives under the coming framework programme Horizon Europe. "Besides doing research, it is important to make the people dream of your goal. Branding is key in order to get visibility towards public authorities and decision makers and thus, increase the chances of getting financial support," explained Jean-François Buggenhout, head of the Flagship unit at DG Connect.

On the way to a handy roadmap

Invited keynote speakers like former IPCC vice-chair Jean-Pascal van Ypersele from UCLouvain, and Harvard University Professor Daniel Nocera were present on the second day. While the Belgian researcher stressed the need for a transition to a net zero emissions' economy through CO₂ storage, the American scientist gave a lecture on carbon-neutral fuels and renewable-based fertilizers. "The world depends on an existing energy infrastructure that has already been paid off. In industrialized countries, renewable energies can piggy-back on it, while in

developing countries stand-alone and distributed devices will be more effective,” highlighted Daniel Nocera.

The talks were followed by an innovation workshop and three parallel roadmapping sessions, where participants were challenged to nurture collectively a comprehensive science and technology roadmap towards a climate neutral economy. The direct exchange with the stakeholders was at the centre of the roadmapping activity. Ongoing discussions should allow the research initiative to adopt and release a dynamic first roadmap’s draft by the end of August 2019. With this document, SUNRISE’s stakeholders will ensure the EU can continue to show leadership in the renewable energy sector.

Energy storage and decarbonisation

On June 20, SUNRISE participated in the EU Sustainable Energy Week both with a stand and a session. The initiative’s coordinator Huub de Groot took part in the panel session ‘Energy storage to boost EU decarbonisation and competitiveness,’ together with representatives of the European research initiatives Battery2030+ and Energy-X.

“We are not yet in the money with solar to fuel, but the market potential is there, on the scale of hundreds of billions yearly. We have to team up with fundamental, applied and industrial research to be there in time learning how to manufacture solar fuels and chemicals for a zero and negative emissions’ circular economy,” concluded Huub de Groot.

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- 3rd Press release: 26 August, 2019, joint press release with ENERGY-X to announce the two initiatives cooperation following the official announcement at Europacat 2019.

SUNRISE & ENERGY-X - Press release

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X joint cooperation: a major step towards building a climate neutral EU

Aachen, August 26, 2019

Representatives from the EU Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) SUNRISE and ENERGY-X announced their joint cooperation on August 20, 2019 during the 14th European Congress on Catalysis, EuropaCat 2019. The two initiatives will continue to pursue their roadmapping actions until February 2020, when they plan to merge in a new initiative, with a new name.

The two projects have already started to coordinate on joint actions. SUNRISE and ENERGY-X representatives took part in the panel discussion of the session: "The Energy-Chemistry Nexus: Towards a European Sustainable Energy & Catalysis Research Initiative", held by ENERGY-X on August 20. Professor Jens Nørskov, coordinator of ENERGY-X, said: ***"It is of utmost importance to unite the efforts within Europe to lay the scientific foundation as well as to foster technological breakthroughs to develop a more sustainable society."***

Both projects share common goals for the conversion of renewable energies into alternative fuels and chemicals. Currently, both initiatives are working together towards a common Manifesto. ***"We need to think long-term and overcome fragmentation"***, explained SUNRISE coordinator Professor Huub de Groot. ***"Several solutions are needed to fight climate change and for that all types of research should team up"***, he added.

Background

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X are two out of the six CSA projects that were selected for the Horizon 2020 call "FETFLAG-01-2018" within the research area of Energy, Environment and Climate Change. Both initiatives received €1 million from the European Commission to develop a detailed proposal for a large-scale research initiative during one year, from March 2019 to February 2020.

Both SUNRISE and ENERGY-X aim to develop sustainable approaches for the storage of renewable energy (solar and wind) through its conversion to fuels and commodity chemicals using abundant molecules such as carbon dioxide, water and nitrogen. The two projects bring together 30 committed organisations, backed by an initial supporting community of approx. 300 stakeholders from academia, industry, and society.

The replacement of fossil fuels and the modernisation of the production processes are crucial to meet the COP 21 Paris Agreement's mission of tackling climate change. A European large-scale initiative is urgently needed to address these key challenges and drive forward major global transformations led by new disruptive technologies.

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- 4th Press release: 13 February, 2020, joint press release with ENERGY-X for the two initiatives joint final event as the SUNERGY kick-off.

SUNRISE & ENERGY-X - Press release

Kick-off of the SUNERGY initiative

Brussels, February 13, 2020

Over 100 stakeholders of the Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) SUNRISE and ENERGY-X gathered on February 5-6, 2020 in Brussels for the kick-off meeting of SUNERGY, a large-scale research and innovation (R&I) initiative in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals. Renewable energy experts from academia, industry and policy addressed the current opportunities and challenges towards decarbonizing the European industry and society over the next 30 years.

The launch event was organized in two sessions: a high-level lunch discussion at the European Parliament (EP) on February 5, and a public two-day conference. The TownHall Europe hosted the afternoon session on February 5, while the morning session on February 6 was hosted by the Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU.

Large-scale R&I initiatives to decarbonize Europe

MEP Morten Helveg Petersen hosted the high-level lunch discussion at the EP. Representatives from both initiatives debated on how large-scale R&I initiatives in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals can contribute to meeting the targets of the Paris Agreement. Keynote speakers were Cristian Silviu Buşoi (ITRE Committee Chair), Hlne Chraye (Directorate Clean Planet of Directorate General Research & Innovation), Mark van Stiphout (Directorate General Energy), Bert Weckhuysen (SUNERGY coordinator), and Maximillian Fleischer (Siemens Energy).

SUNERGY coordinator Bert Weckhuysen: The SUNERGY initiative comes at a time when greater attention to climate and energy issues and on-going developments at European level offer the right framework for action and a great opportunity to join efforts towards reversing climate change.

A common vision to close the carbon and nitrogen cycles

During the public kick-off meeting, the CSAs SUNRISE and ENERGY-X presented their achievements throughout the past year, and proposed their joint vision on providing sustainable and competitive alternatives to fossil fuels by 2050. Keynote speakers like Peter Drll (Director Prosperity, Directorate General Research & Innovation) highlighted the strong support of the European institutions towards R&I to achieve the ambitions of the European Green Deal.

SUNERGY deputy coordinator Frdric Chandezon: This kick-off meeting has served as a key step towards unifying the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X research communities and defining directions for a European large-scale R&I initiative around SUNERGY, within the new European R&I framework Horizon Europe.

Background

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X are two out of the six CSA projects that were selected for the Horizon 2020 call “FETFLAG-01-2018” within the research area of Energy, Environment and Climate Change. Both initiatives received €1 million from the European Commission to develop a detailed proposal for a large-scale research initiative during one year, from March 2019 to February 2020.

Both SUNRISE and ENERGY-X aim to develop sustainable approaches for the storage of renewable energy (solar and wind) through its conversion to fuels and commodity chemicals using abundant molecules such as carbon dioxide, water and nitrogen. The two projects bring together 30 committed organisations, backed by an initial supporting community of approx. 300 stakeholders from academia, industry, and society.

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4.2. Press clippings

4.2.1 Partners' channels

The SUNRISE partners have broadly used their communication channels, and those of their associated institutions, to replicate the press releases, promote the initiative's actions and publish interviews with the involved experts.

English

➤ Leiden University:

- SUNRISE initiative's first stakeholder meeting (21 June 2019): <https://www.universiteitleid.nl/en/news/2019/06/sunrise-initiatives-first-stakeholder-meeting>

➤ Uppsala University:

- SUNRISE selected for European large-scale research initiative (02 February 2019): <https://www.kemi.uu.se/nyheter/enskild-nyhet/?tarContentId=773130>
- Swedish Consortium for Artificial Photosynthesis, The first SUNRISE stakeholder meeting –EU project (17-18 June 2019): <http://www.solarfuel.se/Press/>

➤ IMDEA Energy:

- The Sunrise Stakeholder Workshop took place in Brussels last June 17-18, 2019 (19 June 2019): <https://www.energia.imdea.org/eventos/2019/sunrise-stakeholder-workshop-took-place-brussels-last-june-17-18-2019>

➤ Imperial College:

- Project SUNRISE and accreditation success: News from the College (01 February 2019): <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/190087/project-sunrise-accreditation-success-news-from/>
- SUNRISE teams up with ENERGY-X (30 August 2019): <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/192726/refugee-mental-health-malarial-mysteries-news/#Sunrise>

➤ Fraunhofer IGB:

- Kick-off of the SUNERGY initiative (14 February 2020): <https://www.igb.fraunhofer.de/en/press-media/press-releases/2020/kickoff-sunergy-initiative.html>

➤ Uniwersytet Warszawski:

- SUNRISE's stakeholders first meeting (03 July 2019): <http://en.uw.edu.pl/sunrises-stakeholders-first-meeting/>

D3.3. Dissemination and communication resources

- SUNRISE and ENERGY-X joint cooperation: a major step towards building a climate neutral EU (20 August 2019): <http://en.uw.edu.pl/sunrise-and-energy-x-joint-cooperation-a-major-step-towards-building-a-climate-neutral-eu/>

➤ ICIQ:

- SUNRISE: Solar energy for a circular economy (06 February 2019): <http://www.iciq.org/sunrise-solar-energy-for-a-circular-economy/>
- CERCA: SUNRISE: Solar energy for a circular economy (06 February 2019):
- SUNRISE's first big event (06 July 2019): <http://www.iciq.org/sunrises-first-big-event/>
- CERCA: SUNRISE's first big event (03 July 2019): <http://s368784504.mialojamiento.es/devel/cerca/sunrises-first-big-event/>
- BIST: BIST centre ICIQ part of SUNRISE: Solar energy for a circular economy (09 July 2019): <https://bist.eu/bist-centre-iciq-part-of-sunrise-solar-energy-for-a-circular-economy/>
- SUNRISE and ENERGY-X joint cooperation: a major step towards building a climate neutral EU (30 August 2019): <http://www.iciq.org/sunrise-and-energy-x-joint-cooperation-a-major-step-towards-building-a-climate-neutral-eu/>
- CERCA: SUNRISE and ENERGY-X joint cooperation: a major step towards building a climate neutral EU (30 August 2019): <http://s368784504.mialojamiento.es/devel/cerca/sunrise-and-energy-x-joint-cooperation-a-major-step-towards-building-a-climate-neutral-eu/>
- SUNRISE releases its technological roadmap to a clean energy EU (21 November 2019): <http://www.iciq.org/sunrise-releases-its-technological-roadmap-to-a-clean-energy-eu/>
- BIST: SUNRISE releases its technological roadmap to a clean energy EU (21 November 2019): <https://bist.eu/sunrise-releases-its-technological-roadmap-to-a-clean-energy-eu/>
- Kick-off of the SUNERGY initiative (18 February 2020): <http://www.iciq.org/kick-off-of-the-sunergy-initiative/>

➤ EERA:

- SUNRISE, a preparatory action towards a European large-scale research initiative (01 February 2019): <https://www.eera-set.eu/press-release-sunrise-a-preparatory-action-towards-a-european-large-scale-research-initiative/>
- Thank you to all participants at the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop! (20 June 2019): <https://www.eera-set.eu/thank-you-to-all-participants-at-the-sunrise-stakeholder-workshop/>
- SUNRISE and ENERGY-X joint cooperation: a major step towards building a climate neutral EU (28 August 2019): <https://www.eera-set.eu/press-release-sunrise-and-energy-x-joint-cooperation-a-major-step-towards-building-a-climate-neutral-eu/>
- Kick-off of the SUNERGY initiative (13 February 2020): <https://www.eera-set.eu/news-resources/612:kick-off-of-the-sunergy-initiative.html>

➤ M2i (third party in charge of SUNRISE project management):

- Kick-off SUNERGY (13 February 2020): <https://www.m2i.nl/kick-off-sunergy/>

Dutch

➤ Leiden University:

- SUNRISE: van zonlicht tot smart city (01 February 2019): <https://www.universiteitleidenn.nl/en/news/2019/02/sunrise-from-sunlight-to-smart-city>
- Brandstoffen maken uit zonlicht en CO2: <https://www.universiteitleidenn.nl/research-dossiers/duurzame-energie/brandstoffen-maken-uit-zonlicht-en-co2>
- De kracht van de zon: interview Huub de Groot in Leidraad (07 October 2019): <https://www.universiteitleidenn.nl/nieuws/2019/10/interview-huub-de-groot-in-leidraad>

French

➤ CEA:

- Projet Sunrise : vers l'émergence d'une initiative de recherche Européenne pour produire carburants et produits chimiques par énergie solaire (01 February 2019): <http://www.cea.fr/drf/Pages/Actualites/Vie-de-la-DRF/2019/Projet-Sunrise--vers-l%C3%A9mergence-d-une-initiative-de-recherche-Europ%C3%A9enne-pour-produire-carburants-et-produits-chimiques-pa.aspx>
- Premier grand événement de l'action européenne de coordination et de soutien SUNRISE, au cours de la Semaine de l'énergie durable EUSEW19 (21 June 2019): <http://www.cea.fr/drf/irig/Pages/Actualites/Communiqués-de-presse/Sunrise.aspx>
- IRIG partenaire de l'action européenne de coordination et de soutien (CSA) "SUNRISE" CEA Grenoble (12 July): <http://www.cea.fr/drf/irig/Pages/Actualites/Resultats-scientifiques/2019/Sunrise.aspx>
- Fusion prochaine des "Actions européennes de coordination et de soutien" (CSAs) "SUNRISE" et Energy X (04 September 2019): http://iramis.cea.fr/Phoce/Vie_des_labos/News/index.php?id_news=7630
- SUNRISE publie sa feuille de route technologique pour une énergie propre dans l'UE (14 November 2019): http://www.cea.fr/drf/irig/Pages/Actualites/Resultats-scientifiques/2019/Sunrise_Roadmap.aspx

➤ Empa:

- L'énergie solaire pour une économie circulaire (01 February 2019): <https://www.empa.ch/web/s604/sunrise>

➤ UCLouvain:

D3.3. Dissemination and communication resources

- L'énergie solaire pour une économie circulaire (04 April 2019): <https://uclouvain.be/fr/scienceto-day/actualites/l-energie-solaire-pour-une-economie-circulaire.html>
- Produire de l'énergie via les matières premières disponibles dans l'atmosphère (05 April 2019): <https://cdn.uclouvain.be/groups/cms-editors-presse/cp-avril-2019/05-04-2019%20recherche%20UCLouvain%20%C3%A9nergie%20solaire.pdf>

Italian

➤ CNR:

- SUNRISE, un'azione preparatoria per un grande progetto di ricerca paneuropeo sull'energia solare e l'economia circolare (01 February 2019): <https://www.cnr.it/it/news/8544/sunrise-un-azione-preparatoria-per-un-grande-progetto-di-ricerca-paneuropeo-sull-energia-solare-e-l-economia-circolare>
- Il primo evento organizzato da SUNRISE nell'ambito della 'Settimana europea per la sostenibilità energetica' (26 June 2019): <https://www.cnr.it/it/news/8827>
- Progetto Sunrise: l'esperto John Mathews ospite al Cnr di Bologna (22 July 2019): <https://www.cnr.it/it/news/8873/progetto-sunrise-l-esperto-john-mathews-ospite-al-cnr-di-bologna>
- Verso un'economia circolare: intervista a Nicola Armaroli (18 October 2019): <https://www.cnr.it/it/news/8948?fbclid=IwAR3DfL3FzckQj8Ph5ofgT1PxAyaTf35cYtlhE-RIc6F38gj-TSR49D-nwmLY>

Swedish

➤ Uppsala University:

- SUNRISE - en handlingsplan för ett storskaligt europeiskt forskningsinitiativ (01 February 2019): <https://www.uu.se/nyheter-press/pressmeddelanden/pressmeddelande-visning/?id=4602&area=3&typ=pm&lang=sv>
- Solbränsleforskningen finalist i kampen om stor forskningssatsning från EU. (Interview with Leif Hammarström, 04 February 2019): <https://www.uu.se/nyheter-press/nyheter/artikel/?id=12102&typ=artikel&area=2&lang=sv>

Spanish

➤ IMDEA Energy:

- SUNRISE: Solar Energy for a Circular Economy: <https://www.energia.imdea.org/investigacion/proyectos/sunrise>
- FOTOFUEL Workshop: Current challenges in solar fuels production (10 May 2019): <https://www.energia.imdea.org/eventos/2019/fotofuel-workshop-current-challenges-solar-fuels-production>

- IMDEA Energía participa en la COP25 (26 December 2019): <https://www.energia.imdea.org/eventos/2019/imdea-energia-participa-cop25>
- Lanzamiento de la iniciativa SUNERGY (20 February 2020): <https://www.energia.imdea.org/eventos/2020/lanzamiento-de-iniciativa-sunergy>

German

➤ Empa:

- Solarenergie für die Kreislaufwirtschaft (01 February 2019): <https://www.empa.ch/web/s604/sunrise>

➤ Fraunhofer IGB:

- Projekt SUNRISE: Forscher planen europäische Großforschungsinitiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen und Chemikalien aus Solarenergie (01 February 2019): <https://www.igb.fraunhofer.de/de/presse-medien/presseinformationen/2019/sunrise.html>

➤ Forschungszentrum Jülich:

- Projekt SUNRISE: Forscher planen Europäische Großforschungsinitiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen und Chemikalien aus Solarenergie (07 February 2019): <https://www.fz-juelich.de/Shared-Docs/Pressemitteilungen/UK/DE/2019/2019-02-07-sunrise.html>
- Kooperation zwischen SUNRISE und ENERGY-X: Ein großer Schritt in Richtung „Klimaneutrales Europa“ (21 August 2019): https://www.fz-juelich.de/iek/iek-5/DE/Aktuelles/Meldungen/Dokumente/2019-08-21_Kooperation%20zwischen%20SUNRISE%20und%20ENERGY-X.html

Finnish

➤ Turun Yliopisto:

- Eurooppalaisella yhteistyöllä edistetään aurinkoenergian käyttöä (01 February 2019): <https://www.utu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/mediatiedote/eurooppalaisella-yhteistyolla-edistetaan-aurinkoenergian-kayttoa>
- Turussa pidettävä kansainvälinen fotosynteesikonferenssi pureutuu ihmiskunnan suuriin haasteisiin 22.–24.5 (16 May 2019): <https://www.utu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/mediatiedote/turussa-pidettava-kansainvalinen-fotosynteesikonferenssi-pureutuu>
- Kestävän bioenergian opetus osaksi Turun yliopiston diplomi-insinöörikoulutusta (23 October 2019): <https://www.utu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/uutinen/kestavan-bioenergian-opetus-osaksi-turun-yliopiston-diplomi>
- Kansainvälisellä yhteistyöllä tavoitellaan ilmastoneutraalia Euroopan unionia (02 September 2019): <https://www.utu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/mediatiedote/kansainvalisella-yhteistyolla-tavoitellaan-ilmastoneutraalia-euroopan>

- Tutkijat, päättäjät ja yritykset pohtivat puhtaita energiaratkaisuja Turussa 9.12 (02 December 2019): <https://www.utu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/mediatiedote/tutkijat-paattajat-ja-yritykset-pohtivat-puhtaita-energiaratkaisuja>

Polish

➤ Uniwersytet Warszawski:

- Grant z Horyzontu 2020 dla SUNRISE (01 February 2019): <https://www.uw.edu.pl/grant-z-horyzontu-2020-dla-sunrise/>

Czech

➤ J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry:

- SUNRISE, přípravná akce na evropskou "rozsáhlou výzkumnou iniciativu" (01 February 2019): <https://www.jh-inst.cas.cz/cs/news-press-release/sunrise-pripravna-akce-na-evropskou-rozsahlou-vyzkumnou-iniciativu>

3.2.2. External media

English

- *Energy Post*, SUNRISE, a preparatory action towards a European large-scale research initiative (01 February 2019): <https://energypost.eu/sunrise-a-preparatory-action-towards-a-european-large-scale-research-initiative/>
- *Science and Technology Research News*, SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY (04 February 2019): <https://www.scienceandtechnologyresearchnews.com/solar-energy-for-a-circular-economy/>
- *Nature*, Europe's next €1-billion science projects: six teams make it to final round (11 February 2019): <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-00541-y>
- *Scientific American* (Nature article replication), Europe's next €1-billion science projects: six teams make it to final round (12 February 2019): <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/europes-next-big-budget-science-projects-6-teams-proceed-to-final-round/>
- *Digital Single Market*, Launch of six European initiatives with potential for transformational impact on society and the economy (05 March 2019): <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/launch-six-european-initiatives-potential-transformational-impact-society-and-economy>
- *Science Magazine*, Europe abandons plans for 'flagship' billion-euro research projects (14 May 2019): ciencemag.org/news/2019/05/europe-abandons-plans-flagship-billion-euro-research-projects

- *Chemistry World*, European commission to scrap €1 billion research flagships (31 May 2019): <https://www.chemistryworld.com/news/european-commission-to-scrap-1-billion-research-flagships/3010559.article>
- *CORDIS*, Stakeholder workshop of the SUNRISE "Solar energy for a circular economy" project (1 June 2019): <https://cordis.europa.eu/event/rcn/147090/en>
- *Chemistry World*, Taking a leaf out of plants' books (17 June 2019): <https://www.chemistryworld.com/features/taking-a-leaf-out-of-plants-books/3010612.article>
- *Digital Single Market*, SUNRISE initiative's first stakeholder meeting (25 June 2019): <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/sunrise-initiatives-first-stakeholder-meeting>
- *PhysOrg*, SUNRISE's first big event takes place during the EU Sustainability Energy Week (04 July 2019): <https://phys.org/wire-news/323687494/sunrises-first-big-event-takes-place-during-the-eu-sustainability.html>
- *CORDIS*, SUNRISE initiative (Solar Energy for a Circular Economy) releases its technological roadmap to a clean energy EU (20 November 2019): <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/411577-sunrise-initiative-solar-energy-for-a-circular-economy-releases-its-technological-roadmap-to/en>
- *EU Digital Single Market*, A technological roadmap towards a clean energy European Union (26 November 2019): <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/technological-roadmap-towards-clean-energy-european-union>
- *FETFX*, A roadmap for clean energy (27 November 2019): <http://www.fetfx.eu/news/roadmap-clean-energy/>
- *EU Digital Single Market (Events)*, SUN-ERGY Kick-off event (16 January 2020): <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/sun-ergy-kick-event>
- *FETFX*, Kick-off of the SUNERGY initiative (26 February 2020): <http://www.fetfx.eu/news/kick-off-sunergy-initiative/>

Dutch

- *engineersonline.nl*, Sunrise: van zonlicht tot smart city (04 February 2019): <https://www.engineersonline.nl/nieuws/id31013-sunrise-van-zonlicht-tot-smart-city.html>
- *Bio Based Press*, Biozonnecellen: steeds een stap verder (03 April 2019, interview Huub de Groot): <https://www.biobasedpress.eu/nl/2019/04/biozonnecellen-steeds-een-stap-verder/>
- *Bio Based Press*, Compromis steeds vaker onderdeel van oplossing (12 May 2019, interview Huub de Groot): <https://www.biobasedpress.eu/nl/2019/05/compromis-steeds-vaker-onderdeel-van-oplossing/>

French

- *MyScience*, L'énergie solaire pour une économie circulaire (01 February 2019): https://www.myscience.ch/news/wire/1_energie_solaire_pour_une_economie_circulaire-2019-empa
- *L'avenir.net*, Le projet européen Sunrise décroche un million d'euros (03 February 2019): https://www.lavenir.net/cnt/dmf20190203_01291151/le-projet-europeen-sunrise-decroche-un-million-d-euros
- *La Province*, UCLouvain: le projet européen Sunrise décroche un million d'euros (03 February 2019): <https://www.laprovince.be/341797/article/2019-02-03/uclouvain-le-projet-europeen-sunrise-decroche-un-million-deuros>
- *metro*, Un projet européen pour produire du carburant sans ressources fossiles (04 February 2019): https://sunriseaction.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/metro_30.pdf
- *Batimag*, Le laboratoire fédéral de recherche participe à une initiative européenne (07 February 2019): <https://www.batimag.ch/empa>
- *ee news*, Die Newsplattform für erneuerbare Energien, Lancement de l'avant-projet d'une grande initiative européenne de recherche : L'énergie solaire pour une économie circulaire (09 February 2019): https://www.ee-news.ch/de/article/40407/lancement-de-l-avant-projet-d-une-grande-initiative-europeenne-de-recherche-l-energie-solaire-pour-une-economie-circulaire&page=#article_40407
- *Le Soir*, Transformer le CO2 en ressource inépuisable (04 May 2019): https://sunriseaction.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/CO2-ressource-pageLS_QUOTIDIEN20190504BRUXELLES147.pdf
- *L'EnerGEEK*, FERMER LE CYCLE DU CARBONE, UNE SOLUTION POUR L'ACCORD DE PARIS? (30 May): <https://lenergeek.com/2019/05/30/cycle-carbone-accord-paris-total/>

Italian

- *Energia Rinnovabili.it*, L'iniziava di ricerca Sunrise sarà la base per grande progetto di ricerca paneuropeo dedicato all'innovazione (04 February 2019): <http://www.rinnovabili.it/energia/sunrise-energia-solare-economia-circolare/>
- *Campus Rieti*, SUNRISE, un'azione preparatoria per un grande progetto di ricerca paneuropeo sull'energia solare e l'economia circolare (06 February 2019): <https://www.campus.rieti.it/jw/notizie/attualita/12308-sunrise-un-azione-preparatoria-per-un-grande-progetto-di-ricerca-paneuropeo-sull-energia-solare-e-l-economia-circolare>
- *Radio Città del Capo*, Adattamenti. Sunrise: il progetto europeo per produrre carburanti con la fotosintesi (15 July 2019, Interview Nicola Armaroli): <https://www.radiocittadelcapo.it/archives/adattamenti-sunrise-il-progetto-europeo-per-produrre-carburanti-con-la-fotosintesi->

[205666/?fbclid=IwAR1uebTqInsijQ84C9SvDK-WNwJWjYghWiG_RzPsczYanKkaX5O0Ni-LPE3Q](https://www.facebook.com/205666/?fbclid=IwAR1uebTqInsijQ84C9SvDK-WNwJWjYghWiG_RzPsczYanKkaX5O0Ni-LPE3Q)

- *UNIBO Magazine*, Verso l'industria solare: realizzato un sistema ad alta efficienza che produce idrogeno e composti chimici ad alto valore aggiunto (24 February 2020): <https://magazine.unibo.it/archivio/2020/02/24/verso-12019industria-solare-realizzato-un-sistema-ad-alta-efficienza-che-produce-idrogeno-e-composti-chimici-ad-alto-valore-aggiunto>

Polish

- Nauka W Polsce, Słoneczne związki ze sztucznego liścia: mobilizacja firm i naukowców, by ulepszyć fotosyntezę (10 April 2020): <http://naukawpolsce.pap.pl/aktualnosci/news,81656,sloneczne-zwiazki-ze-sztucznego-liscia-mobilizacja-firm-i-naukowcow-ulepszyt>

Swedish

- Almedalen.se, SUNRISE gör det möjligt att skala upp teknik för solbränsle (01 July 2019): <https://almedalen.se/sunrise-gor-det-mojligt-att-skala-upp-teknik-for-solbransle/>

Spanish

- *Radio Internacional*, ¿Qué es la fotosíntesis artificial? (04 July 2019, Interview Victor de la Peña): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SwW6-uM5daY&feature=youtu.be>
- *InnovaSpain*, Imitar a las plantas para conseguir el combustible del futuro (04 July 2019): <https://www.innovaspain.com/imitar-a-las-plantas-para-conseguir-el-combustible-del-futuro/>
- *Madri+d*, SUNRISE: Energía Solar para una economía circular (16 July 2019): <http://www.madri-masd.org/blogs/energiasalternativas/2019/07/16/133983>
- *Catalunya Press*, Nuestra calidad de vida depende de que resolvamos el problema del cambio climático (06 September 2019, Interview Julio Lloret): <https://www.catalunyapress.es/texto-diario/mostrar/1519704/nuestra-calidad-vida-depende-resolvamos-problema-cambio-climatico>
- *Radio 5*, Proyecto SUNRISE: energía limpia imitando la Naturaleza (05 December 2019, Interview at COP25 with Víctor de la Peña and Laura López): <https://www.rtve.es/alicarta/audios/todo-noticias-manana/proyecto-sunrise-energia-limpia-imitando-naturaleza/5460219/>
- *Radio 3*, suena por el planeta (06 December 2019, Interview at COP25 with Víctor de la Peña): <https://www.rtve.es/alicarta/audios/radio-3-suena-por-el-planeta/radio-3-suena-planeta-patax-sandra-carrasco-enrique-paco-soto-manolo-garcia-06-12-19/5461529/>
- *TVE2, Lab 24*, Reportaje: Copiando la naturaleza (09 December 2019, Interview with Elisabet Romero): <https://www.rtve.es/alicarta/videos/lab24/lab24-reportaje-copiando-naturaleza/5462164/>
- *InnovaSpain*, Macroproyecto europeo para la obtención de combustibles limpios imitando a la fotosíntesis (26 February 2020): <https://www.innovaspain.com/proyecto-sunergy-fotosintesis-artificial/>

German

- *Punkt 4 info*, Solarenergie soll Kreislaufwirtschaft antreiben (01 February 2019): <https://punkt4.info/social-news/news/solarenergie-soll-kreislaufwirtschaft-antreiben.html>
- *Energycluster.ch*, SOLARENERGIEFORSCHUNG IM GROSSEN STIL (02 February 2019): <https://www.energie-cluster.ch/de/medien/news/solarenergieforschung-im-grossen-stil-2588-5237.html>
- *Windkraft-Journal*, Europäische Grossforschungsinitiative SUNRISE: Solarenergie für die Kreislaufwirtschaft (02 February 2019): <https://www.windkraft-journal.de/2019/02/02/europaeische-grossforschungsinitiative-sunrise-solarenergie-fuer-die-kreislaufwirtschaft/132322>
- *idw – Informationsdienst Wissenschaft*, Projekt SUNRISE: Forscher planen Europäische Großforschungsinitiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen (07 February 2019): <https://idw-online.de/de/news?print=1&id=710284>
- *Öbu*, Gastbeitrag: Solarenergie für die Kreislaufwirtschaft (07 February 2019): <https://www.oebu.ch/de/news/aktuelle-news/gastbeitrag-solarenergie-fuer-die-kreislaufwirtschaft-4162.html>
- *Logistik-express*, Forscher planen Europäische Großforschungsinitiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen (08 February 2019): <https://www.logistik-express.com/forscher-planen-europaeische-grossforschungsinitiative-zu-synthetischen-kraftstoffen/?hilite=%27sunrise%27>
- *ee news, Die Newsplattform für erneuerbare Energien*, Solarenergie für Kreislaufwirtschaft: Sunrise ebnet Weg für solarbasierte Treibstoffe und chemische Produkte (09 February 2019): <https://www.ee-news.ch/de/erneuerbare/article/40404/solarenergie-fur-die-kreislaufwirtschaft-sunrise-ebnet-den-weg-zu-solarbasierten-treibstoffen-und-chemischen-produkten>
- *Internationales Verkehrswesen*, SUNRISE: Großforschungs-Initiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen (10 February 2019): <https://www.internationales-verkehrswesen.de/sunrise-grossforschungsinitiative/>
- *Process Vogel*, Forschungsinitiative zur Produktion von synthetischen Kraftstoffen steht in den Startlöchern (11 February 2019): <https://www.process.vogel.de/forschungsinitiative-zur-produktion-von-synthetischen-kraftstoffen-steht-in-den-startloechern-a-798232/>
- *Energiefirmen.de*, Forscher planen europäische Initiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen (11 February 2019): <https://www.energiefirmen.de/news/nachrichten/artikel-35798-forscher-planen-europische-initiative-zu-synthetischen-kraftstoffen>
- *SolarServer*, Solarenergie für Kraftstoffe und Chemie (11 February 2019): <https://www.solar-server.de/2019/02/11/solarenergie-fuer-kraftstoffe-und-chemie/>
- *Iwr*, Forscher planen europäische Initiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen (11 February 2019): <https://www.iwr.de/news.php?id=35798>

- *Analytik News*, Europäische Großforschungsinitiative zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen und Chemikalien aus Solarenergie (12 February 2019): <https://analytik.news/Presse/2019/92.html>
- *Kloepfel 4PL Solutions*, Großprojekt zu synthetischen Kraftstoffen (12 February 2019): https://sunriseaction.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Gro%C3%9Fprojekt-zu-synthetischen-Kraftstoffen- -Kloepfel-4PL-Solutions_52.pdf
- *Industriemedien, Briefing one*, Interview with Hervé Bercegol, SUNRISE deputy coordinator: "Storing renewable energy in molecules is the most convenient solution" (21 May 2019), English version: <https://sunriseaction.com/blog/>

Finnish

- *Aamuset*, Eurooppalaisella yhteistyöllä edistetään aurinkoenergian käyttöä (01 February 2019): <https://aamuset.fi/uutiset/4467444/Eurooppalaisella+yhteistyolla+edistetaan+aurinkoenergian+kayttoa>
- *Turun Sanomat*, Turku vahvasti mukana puhtaan energian tutkimuksessa (01 September 2019): <https://www.ts.fi/mielipiteet/aliot/4686140/Turku+vahvasti+mukana+puhtaan+energian+tutkimuksessa>

Czech

- *Akademie věd České republiky*, Evropský projekt se zaměří na výrobu paliv z dostupných surovin (05 February 2019): <https://avcr.cz/cs/o-nas/aktuality/Evropsky-projekt-se-zameri-na-vyrobu-paliv-z-dostupnych-surovin>
- *Solární Novinky.cz*, Evropský projekt SUNRISE podpoří rozvoj solární energetiky a akumulace (07 February 2019): <http://www.solarninovinky.cz/?zpravy/2019020702/evropsky-projekt-s>
- *Volty.cz*, Evropský projekt SUNRISE zaměřený na solární energii obdrží milion Eur (09 February 2019): <https://www.volty.cz/2019/02/09/evropsky-projekt-sunrise-zamereny-na-solarni-energii-obdrzi-milion-eur/>
- *Věda výzkum*, Evropský projekt se zaměří na výrobu paliv z dostupných surovin (10 February 2019): <https://vedavyzkum.cz/blogy-a-rozhovory/akademie-ved-cr/evropsky-projekt-se-zameri-na-vyrobu-paliv-z-dostupnych-surovin>
- *Česká věda do světa*, Evropský projekt se zaměří na výrobu paliv z dostupných surovin (10 February 2019): <http://ceskavedadosveta.cz/evropsky-projekt-se-zameri-na-vyrobu-paliv-z-dostupnych-surovin/>
- *Parlamentní Listy.cz*, Akademie věd: Evropský projekt výroby paliv z dostupných surovin (10 February 2019): <https://www.parlamentnilisty.cz/zpravy/tiskovezpravy/Akademie-ved-Evropsky-projekt-vyroby-paliv-z-dostupnych-surovin-569990>

- *EnviWeb*, Evropský projekt SUNRISE zaměřený na solární energii obdrží milion Eur (18 February 2019): <http://www.enviweb.cz/113155>
- *Prumyslovaekologie*, Evropský projekt SUNRISE zaměřený na solární energii obdrží milion Eur (10 April 2019): <https://www.prumyslovaekologie.cz/transfer.asp?aspxerrorpath=/Dokument/105904/co2-nemusi-byt-problemem-ale-i-moznou-surovinou-pro-dalsi-zpracovani.aspx>

Catalan

- *RAC1, Via Lliure*, D'aquí 10 anys: com consumirem energia (17 February 2019): <https://www.rac1.cat/a-la-carta/detail/f4c986a2-bf56-475a-9537-dcb99c90b722?program=via-lliure§ion=d-aqui-10-anys>
- *Gencat, Departament d'Acció Exterior, Relacions Institucionals i Transparència*, Ja es coneixen les sis iniciatives escollides per la Comissió Europea pel seu potencial d'impacte transformador en la societat i l'economia (07 March 2019): http://exteriors.gencat.cat/ca/ambits-dactuacio/afers-exteriors/ue/fons_europeus/detalls/noticia/20190307_noves-FET
- *Gencat*, Projecte Sunrise: producció de combustible i de químics de base a partir de l'energia solar (17 June 2019): <http://territori.gencat.cat/ca/detalls/Article/energyxsunrise#bloc2>
- *Tarragona Ràdio*, Combustible i productes químics simulant la fotosíntesi de les plantes (04 September 2019): https://www.tarragonaradio.cat/contingut/combustible_i_productes_quimics_simulant_la_fotosintesi_de_les_plantes/19168
- *TAC12 TV*, Investigadors de l'ICIQ volen crear combustibles simulant una fotosíntesi artificial (06 September 2019): <https://tac12.tv/tarragona/arxiu-tarragona/item/9743-investigadors-de-la-urv-volen-crear-combustibles-a-partir-d-aigua-i-co2-alimentats-per-llum-solar>
- *Catalunya Ràdio*, En un futur, els cotxes funcionaran amb energies renovables? (04 October 2019): <https://www.ccma.cat/catrado/alacarta/el-mati-de-catalunya-radio/en-un-futur-els-cotxes-funcionaran-amb-energies-renovables/audio/1050909/>
- *La Xarxa*, Cinc cèntims / 203 - Nous combustibles (08 October 2019): <http://www.alacarta.cat/cinc-centims/capitol/cinc-centims-203-nous-combustibles>
- *Ràdio Ciutat Tarragona*, Crear energia a partir de fotosíntesi artificial (09 October 2019): <https://rctgn.cat/crear-energia-a-partir-de-fotosintesi-artificial/>
- *Ràdio Cambrils*, Ones de ciència. (23 October 2019): <http://radiocambrils.alacarta.cat/onesdecienca/capitol/ones-de-ciencia-capitol-3-amb-laura-lopez-i-amelia-ochoa>
- *Ara*, Copiar la natura per ajudar el planeta (13 November 2019): https://www.ara.cat/campdetarragona/Copiar-natura-ajudar-planeta_0_2343365660.html

5. SUNRISE STAKEHOLDERS WORKSHOP

5.1. Agenda

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop Agenda, June 17-18, 2019

Dates: 17-18/06/2019

Location: Brussels

Address: Palais des Académies, rue Ducale 1, 1000 Bruxelles

Monday, June 17

9:30 – 10:00 am

Welcome, coffee

10:00 – 10:15 am

Opening address

Huub de Groot | Leiden University

10:15 – 12:45 pm

SUNRISE Consolidated vision

Chair: Nicola Armaroli | National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

Speakers:

- Marc Fontecave | College de France, Paris
- Roel van de Krol | Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
- Marcella Bonchio | University of Padova
- Jens Nørskov | Technical University of Denmark

Wrap-up session

12:45– 2:00 pm

Lunch

2:00 – 4:00 pm

SUNRISE Roadmap

Chair: Hervé Bercegol | French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (CEA)

Speakers:

- Damien Dallemagne | CO₂ Value Europe
- Niek van Hulst | The Institute of Photonic Sciences (ICFO)
- Sophia Haussener | École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
- Michel Gimenez | LafargeHolcim

Wrap-up session

4:00 – 4:30 pm

Coffee break

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop Agenda, June 17-18, 2019

4:30 – 6:00 pm

SUNRISE Governance workshop

This session aims at addressing the governance of a large-scale research initiative, for example a future mission under Horizon Europe. It will start with an introduction followed by a panel discussion with representatives of the European Commission, member states and associated countries, representatives of industry and flagship – also involving the audience.

Chairs: Frédéric Chandezon (CEA) and Laura Lopez | Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ)

Speakers:

- Jean-François Buggenhout | DG Connect, European Commission
- Lars Klüver | Danish Board of Technology Foundation
- Paulina Styczeń | Department of Innovation and Development of the Poland's Ministry of Science and Higher Education
- Andreas Förster | DECHEMA
- Marcel Hoek | Dutch Research Council (NWO)
- Max Lemme | Scientific Secretary of the Strategic Advisory Council and former leader of the Graphene Flagship Partnering Division

6:00 – 8:00 pm

Networking dinner

Tuesday, June 18

8:30 – 9:00 am

Welcome, coffee

9:00 – 9:30 am

The urgency of the climate challenge: Why zero net emissions are needed?

Jean-Pascal van Ypersele, Former IPCC Vice-Chair, Full professor of climatology and environmental sciences at UCLouvain, Belgium, and Member of the Belgian Royal Academy.

9:30 – 10:30 am

Views from the SUNRISE community: Pitches from SUNRISE supporters

Chairs: Anita Schneider | European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) and Frédéric Chandezon (CEA)

Speakers:

- Robert Kourist | TU Graz
- Merja Penttilä | VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
- David Waroquiers | MaDeSo
- David Ayme-Perrot | Total
- Marc Robert | Université Paris Diderot

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop Agenda, June 17-18, 2019

- Hannah Johnson | Toyota Motor Europe
- Klaas J. Hellingwerf | Photanol
- Martin Roeb | DLR Institute of Solar Research
- Christoph Beuttler | Climeworks
- Pierdomenico Biasi | Casale SA
- Elisabet Romero | Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ)
- Paolo Bombelli | University of Cambridge
- Astrid Bjørnsen | Wald Schnee und Landschaft WSL

10:30 – 11:00 am

Coffee break

11:00 – 12:45 pm

Innovation workshop

Chairs: Antonino Ardilio | Fraunhofer and Elfriede Simon | Siemens

- Introduction
- SUNRISE Innovation Strategy | Yvonne Wich | Fraunhofer
- SUNRISE Innovation Process Design

12:45 – 2:00 pm

Lunch

2:00 – 2:30 pm

Scientific presentation

Daniel Nocera | Harvard University

2:30 – 4:00 pm

Road mapping workshop

Chair: Carina Faber | UCLouvain

Three parallel sessions:

- **Hydrogen and ammonia production**
Salle Roi Baudoin
- **CO₂ capture and electrochemical conversion**
Patio
- **Solar direct conversion via bio-, biohybrid- and integrated photoelectrochemical devices**
Salle Prigogine

4:00 – 5:00 pm

Closing Coffee, networking

5.2. Registration list

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop – List of Attendees

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Alessandro	ABBOTTO	Univ. Milano-Bicocca
Stephan	ABERMANN	AIT - Austrian Institute of Technology
Yagut	ALLAHVERDIYEVA-RINNE	University of Turku
Teresa	ANDREU	Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC)
Antonino	ARDILIO	Fraunhofer IAO
Nicola	ARMAROLI	CNR
Eva-Mari	ARO	University of Turku
Vincent	ARTERO	CEA
David	AYME-PERROT	TOTAL SA
Stefan	BAUMANN	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
Patrick	BEHR	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
Thierry	BELMONTE	Université de Lorraine
Herve	BERCEGOL	CEA
Christoph	BEUTTLER	Climeworks
Michal	BIALKOWSKI	CASALE SA
Pierdomenico	BIASI	CASALE SA
Anja	BIEBERLE	DIFFER
Laurent I'Pad	BILLON	IPREM UMR 5254
Astrid	BJÖRNSEN GURUNG	Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL
Jonathan	BLOH	DECHEMA-Forschungsinstitut
Paolo	BOMBELLI	University of Cambridge
Audrey	BONDUELLE	IFP Energies nouvelles
Artur	BRAUN	Empa
Jean-François	BUGGENHOUT	European Commission, DG CNECT
Urs	CABALZAR	Empa
David	CANNELLA	Universite Libre de Bruxelles
Thibault	CANTAT	CEA, Université Paris-Saclay
Aura	CARAMIZARU	JRC
Flavia	CASSIOLA	Shell New Energies Research & Technology
Daniela	CAVALCOLI	University of Bologna, Physics and Astronomy Dept
Christine	CAVAZZA	LCBM-CEA Grenoble
Federico	CERNUSCHI	RSE
Stephane	CHAMPLONG	Solvay, Corporate R&I
Frédéric	CHANDEZON	CEA
Murielle	CHAVAROT-KERLIDOU	CEA
Athanassios	COUSOLELOS	University of Crete
Kilian	CRONE	Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH (dena)
Damien	DALLEMAGNE	CO2 Value Europe
Simon	DE CORTE	Ghent University
Lieve	DE DONCKER	UHasselt
Huub	DE GROOT	Leiden University
Iulia	DEGERATU	Materials Innovation Institute (M2i)
Jean-Paul	DELATTRE	ICE France
Herve	DESVAUX	CEA

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop – List of Attendees

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Mmanstsae Moche	DIALE	SARCHI: Clean and Green Energy
Stefania	DOPPIU	CIC energuGUNE
Simon M.-M.	DUBOIS	CNRS
James	DURRANT	Imperial College London
Selma	ERAT	Mersin University
Emilie	ETOUNDI	GreenWin
Carina	FABER	UCLouvain
Pau	FARRÀS COSTA	NUI Galway
Verena	FENNEMANN	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft
Giovani	FINAZZI	CEA
Maximilian	FLEISCHER	Siemens AG
Marc	FORTECAVE	College de france
Andreas	FÖRSTER	DECHEMA
Laia	FRANCESCH	UPPA
Fernando	FRESNO	IMDEA Energy
Vinciane	GAILLARD	European University Association
Michel	GIMENEZ	LafargeHolcim
John	GREGOIRE	Joint Center for Artificial Photosynthesis, Caltech
Alexa	GRIMM	Utrecht University
Elena	GUARNERI	Technical University of Denmark DTU
Kirstin	GUTEKUNST	University of Kiel
Katja	HAAS-SANTO	Karlsruhe Institute of Technolgy - KIT
Ken	HAENEN	Hasselt University
Leif	HAMMARSTRÖM	Uppsala University
Anna	HANKIN	Imperial College London
An	HARDY	Hasselt University
Sophia	HAUSSENER	EPFL
Klaas Jan	HELLINGWERF	Photanol BV
Patrick	HENDRICK	ULB
Benjamin	HERZHAFT	IFPEN
Marcel	HOEK	Dutch Research Council (NWO)
Winfried	HOKE	European Climate Research Alliance (ECRA)
Holger	IHSEN	KIT
Philippe	JACQUES	EMIRI
Paul	JANSSEN	SCK•CEN
Hannah	JOHNSON	Toyota Motor Europe
Christoph	JUGEL	Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH (dena)
Andreas	KAFIZAS	Imperial College London
Joanna	KARGUL	University of Warsaw
Harald	KERP	M2i
Sachin	KINGE	Toyota Motor Europe
Lars	KLÜVER	Danish Board of Technology Foundation
Henrik	KOCH	NTNU

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop – List of Attendees

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Matthieu	KOEPP	CEA
Robert	KOURIST	TU Graz
Mark	KOZDRAS	Natural Resources Canada
Winfried	LEIBL	CEA
Max	LEMME	RWTH Aachen University / AMO GmbH
Fabrice	LEMOINE	University of Lorraine / CPU
Hélène	LEPAUMIER	ENGIE Laborelec
Axel	LÖFBERG	Univ. Lille
Laura	LOPEZ	ICIQ - Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia
Philippe	LORGE	H2WIN S.A.
Ann	MAGNUSON	Uppsala university
Aizhan	MAMYRKHANOVA	EERA
Haresh	MANYAR	Queen's University Belfast
Bonchio	MARCELLA	University of Padova
Jordi	MARTORELL	ICFO
Sergio	MASTROIANNI	Solvay
Kim	MCKELVEY	Trinity College Dublin
Marcel	MEEUS	EMIRI
Sen	MEI	SINTEF
Juergen	MEINHARDT	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft
Tahar	MELLITI	Atmostat
Jan	MERTENS	ENGIE
Carmen	MILLAN CHACARTEGUI	INEA
Francesc	MOLINS	HS Osnabrueck
Engin	MOLVA	CEA & ANCRE
Joan Ramon	MORANTE	IREC
Paul	MOREUX	TEK4Life
Alberto	NALDONI	RCPTM-Palacky University Olomouc
Amin	NASIRI	LEITAT Technological Center
Daniel	NOCERA	Harvard University, US
Timothy	NOEL	Eindhoven University of Technology
Greta	NOELKE	Fraunhofer IME
Federico	NORIS	IREC
Jens	NØRSKOV	Technical University of Denmark
Amelia	OCHOA	ICIQ
Fabrice	ODOBEL	CEISAM-CNRS
Christian	OEHR	Fraunhofer IGB
Raffaele	OSTUNI	CASALE SA
Deepak	PANT	Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO)
Alessandro	PARENTE	Université Libre de Bruxelles
Thomas	PELLERIN-CARLIN	INSTITUT JACQUES DELORS
Merja	PENTTILÄ	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
Anastasios	PERIMENIS	Université libre de Bruxelles
Tomasz	POPRAWKA	PolSCA - Polish Science Contact Agency

SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop – List of Attendees

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Gian-Marco	RIGNANESE	Université catholique de Louvain
Marc	ROBERT	Université Paris Diderot
Martin	ROEB	DLR
Elisabet	ROMERO	Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia
Arne	ROTH	Bauhaus Luftfahrt e.V.
Saida	SAHRARI	Umicore
Manel	SANMARTI	IREC
Cosimo	SBANO	IChemE Clean Energy SIG
Philippe	SCHILD	EC DG R&I
Thomas	SCHLEKER	European Commission
Anita	SCHNEIDER	EERA
Paul	SCHREURS	VLAIO
Anastasia	SENDREA	European Commission
Sharavanan	SHANMUGAM	Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH (dena)
Ian	SHARP	Technical University of Munich
Amin	SHAVANDI	Université libre de Bruxelles
Guilherme	SIEPIERSKI	Solvay
Elfriede	SIMON	Siemens AG
Abdelilah	SLAOUI	CNRS
Yoan	STANEV	European Energy Research Alliance
Ludmilla	STEIER	Imperial College London
Véronique	STERCK	SOLVAY R&I Centre Brussels
Paulina	STYCZEŃ	Department of Innovation and Development of the Poland's Ministry of Science and Higher Education
Tekla	TAMMELIN	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
Geoff	THORNTON	University College London
Marc	TORRELL	IREC
Rita	TOTH	Empa
Roel	VAN DE KROL	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie GmbH
Bart	VAN DEN BOSCH	Avantium
Jarl Ivar	VAN DER VLUGT	University of Amsterdam
Niek	VAN HULST	ICFO - Institute of Photonic Sciences
Jean-Pascal	VAN YPERSELE	UCLouvain
Antonin	VLCEK	J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry, Prague
Thomas	VRANKEN	Hasselt University
David	WAROQUIERS	Materials Design Solutions
Yvonne	WICH	Fraunhofer IAO
Petra	ZAPP	Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH
Dirk	ZIEGENBALG	Ulm University

6. SUNERGY KICK-OFF MEETING (Final joint event SUNRISE & ENERGY-X)

6.1. Agenda

SUNERGY policy lunch event at the European Parliament

- *Decarbonising Europe: How large-scale R&I initiatives on fossil-free fuels and chemicals can contribute to the European Green Deal*

Focus of the event

To facilitate a broader discussion between decision makers, academia, industry and other key stakeholders

- Hosted by Morten Helveg Petersen (MEP, Denmark)

5 February 13.00 – 14.30 European Parliament

By invitation only

SUNERGY public kick-off event

- *Fossil-free fuels and chemicals for a climate-neutral Europe*

Focus of the event

Focus will be on the operational side, looking at the roadmaps and achievements of the ENERGY-X and SUNRISE CSAs and presenting how cooperation will continue through SUN-ERGY (envisaged roadmap of the initiative, ways to involve stakeholders etc.).

Preliminary programme:

Day 1: February 5, 16.00 – 18.00

TownHall Europe, Square de Meeus, Brussels, 5 February: 16.00 – 18.00 – followed by a networking reception

15.30 – 16.00	Registration and coffee
16.00 – 16.10	Welcome (Bert Weckhuysen, SUNERGY coordinator, Utrecht University)
16.10 – 16.30	SUNERGY (Frédéric Chandezon, SUNERGY deputy coordinator, CEA)
16.30 – 17.00	Perspective from industry - Jan Mertens, ENGIE
17.00 – 17.30	Perspective from European Commission - Peter Dröll, Director Prosperity, DG RTD
17.30 – 17.55	Q&A
17.55 – 18.00	Wrap-up
18.00 – 20.00	Networking reception

Day 2: February 6, 9.00 – 14.00

The Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU, Brussels, 21 Rue Montoyer

9.00 – 9.30	Registration and coffee
9.30 – 9.40	Opening Address (Johannes Bade, Head of Unit Higher Education, Research and the Arts, Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU)
9.40 – 10.00	SUN-ERGY Vision (Bert Weckhuysen, SUNERGY coordinator, Utrecht University)
10.00 – 11.00	SUN-ERGY Implementation approach - Ramp-up phase leading to a large scale initiative (Gabriele Centi, ERIC) - Starting point of implementation: key elements of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X roadmaps (Hervé Bercegol, CEA) - Q&A
11.00 – 11.30	Coffee Break
11.30 – 11.50	Presentation Photo-contest winner (Amedeo Agosti, University of Bologna)
11.50 – 13.00	Short presentations by recently awarded projects in the area followed by a round table discussion (Moderator: Joanna Kargul, Warsaw University): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE-NMBP-25-2019: Photocatalytic synthesis, awarded project 'DistributEd Chemicals And fuels production from CO2 in photoelectrocatalytic Devices' (Siglinda Perathoner, ERIC) - LC-SC3-RES-29-2019: Converting Sunlight to storable chemical energy, awarded project 'Novel photo-assisted systems for direct Solar-driven redUction of CO2 to energy rich CHEMicals' (Huub de Groot, Leiden University) - ITN-2019: Awarded project 'Training the next generation of scientists in solar chemicals for a sustainable Europe by hybrid molecule/semiconductor devices' (Pau Farràs, NUI Galway) - ITN-2016: Awarded project 'Electrochemical Conversion of Renewable Electricity into Fuels and Chemicals' (Petr Krtil, J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry) - LC-SC3-CC-1-2018: Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) aspects of the Clean-Energy Transition, awarded project 'COllective action Models for Energy Transition and Social Innovation' (Merce Almuni, VITO-Energyville)
13.00 – 14.00	Lunch

With the friendly support of the Representation of the State of Hessen to the European Union

6.2. Registration List

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Alessandro	ABBOTTO	University of Milano-Bicocca
Stephan	ABERMANN	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
Amedeo	AGOSTI	University of Bologna
Marten	AHLQUIST	KTH Royal Insitute of Technology
Yagut	ALLAVERDIYEVA-RINNE	University of Turku
Michele	ARESTA	IC2R srl
Nicola	ARMAROLI	CNR
Eva-Mari	ARO	University of Turku
Vincent	ARTERO	CEA
Nicolas	AUGE	CEA
Oytun	BABACAN	Imperial College London
Corsin	BATTAGLIA	Empa
Stefan	BAUMANN	Foschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
Didier	BELOIN-SAINT-PIERRE	Empa
Hervé	BERCEGOL	CEA
Davide	BERTUCCIO	freelance
Astrid	BJØRNSEN	Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL
Patrick	BOURREL	European Commission
Søren	BØWADT	European Commission
Artur	BRAUN	Empa
Lars	BRÜCKNER	DTU
Gabriele	CENTI	ERIC aisbl
Frédéric	CHANDEZON	CEA
Arnold	CHOI	ExxonMobil
Sacha	CORBY	Imperial College London
Athanassios	COUSOLELOS	University of Crete
Estibaliz	CRESCO	CIC Energigune
DAMIEN	DALLEMAGNE	CO2 Value Europe
Giovanna	D'ANGELO	University of Messina
Simon	DE CORTE	Ghent University
Lieve	DE DONCKER	UHasselt
Huub	DE GROOT	Leiden University
Gaëlle	DECROIX	CEA
Angela	DIBENEDETTO	CIRCC
Stefania	DOPPIU	CICenergigUNE
Nicholas	DUMMER	Cardiff University
Nicolas	DUPUY	Université de Lorraine
James	DURRANT	Imperial college london

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Peter	ELLIS	Johnson Matthey
Carina	FABER	UCLouvain
Umar	FAROOQ	jamia millia islamia
Pau	FARRAS	NUI Galway
Max	FLEISCHER	Siemens
Fernando	FRESNO	IMDEA Energy Institute
Manuel	FRONDEL	RWI - Leibniz-Institute for Economic Research
Jelizaveta	GAMALEJEVA	Eurideas
Sebastian	GOEKE	Applied Materials
Gideon	GRADER	Technion
Alexa	GRIMM	Utrecht University
Elena	GUARNERI	Technical University of Denmark
Anna	HANKIN	Imperial College London
Jan Erik	HANSSEN	1-Tech SPRL
Sean	HENNESSEY	NUI Galway
Han	HUYNH	ENGIE Laborelec
Holger	IHSSEN	Helmholtz Association
Philippe	JACQUES	EMIRI
Paul	JANSSEN	SCK•CEN
Nicolas	JEULAND	SAFRAN
Pablo	JIMENEZ-CALVO	Solid States Laboratory, University Paris Saclay
Joachim	JOHN	IMEC
Hannah	JOHNSON	Toyota Motor Europe
Marcus	JUVANCIC	Fraunhofer e.V.
Joanna	KARGUL	Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw
Stanislaw	KARPIŃSKI	Warsaw University of Life Sciences, Institute of Biology
Pasi	KEINÄNEN	Tampere University
Harald	KERP	MZI
Florian	KIEFER	Empa
Andrej	KOBE	EC DG ENV
Petr	KRTIL	J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical chemistry
Michael	KYRIAKOPOULOS	European Commission
Lars	LAUTERBACH	Technische Universität Berlin
Julio	LLORET	ICIQ - Institut of Chemical Research of Catalonia
Axel	LÖFBERG	Univ. Lille
Laura	LOPEZ	ICIQ
Ann	MAGNUSON	Uppsala university
Haresh	MANYAR	Queen's University Belfast

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
Guy	MARIN	Ghent University
Roeb	MARTIN	DLR
BERTA	MARTÍNEZ	CSIC
Jordi	MARTORELL	ICFO
Ivan	MATEJAK	EERA aisbl
Jan	MERTENS	ENGIE CC
Joan Ramon	MORANTE	IREC
Poul Georg	MOSES	Haldor Topsoe
Sabrina	MÜLLER	DECHEMA e.V.
Sophia	NEUMANN	Representation of the State of Saxony-Anhalt to the EU
Huu Chuong (Bob)	NGUYEN	Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ)
Kathrine Bjerregaard	NIELSEN	Technical University of Denmark
Andrea	NOGOVA	Palacky University Olomouc, Regional Centre for Advanced Technologies and Materials
Jens	NØRSKOV	Technical University of Denmark
AMELIA	OCHOA	ICIQ
Bart	ONSIA	imec
Bilal	OUTIRBA	Université Libre de Bruxelles
Alessandro	PARENTE	Université Libre de Bruxelles
Luca	PASQUINI	University of Bologna
Siglinda	PERATHONER	ERIC aisbl
Anastasios	PERIMENIS	CO2 Value Europe
Simon	PERRAUD	CEA-Liten
LORGE	PHILIPPE	H2WIN SA
Virginia	POGGI	Università di Bologna
Tomasz	POPRAWKA	PolSCA
Martina	RÁDLI	Utrecht University
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Bruno	ROBERT	CEA
Martin	ROEB	DLR
Dorota	RUTKOWSKA-ZBIK	Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry PAS
Svetlana	SAMSONOVA	Port of Antwerp
Alessandra	SANSON	CNR-DSCTM
Micheal	SCANLON	University of Limerick
Philippe	SCHILD	European Commission - DG Research and Innovation
Anita	SCHNEIDER	EERA

First Name	Last Name	Organisation
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Alessandro	SENOCRATE	EMPA
Guilherme	SIEPIERSKI	Solvay
Alexandra	SIMON	WindEurope
Minas	STYLIANAKIS	Hellenic Mediterranean University
Piotr	SWIATEK	New European Energy
Ludovic	TROIAN-GAUTIER	Université libre de bruxelles
Annette	TRUNSCHKE	Fritz-Haber-Institut der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Berlin
Yoed	TSUR	Technion - Israel Institute of Technology
richard	VAN DE SANDEN	DIFFER-TU/e
Alexander	VAN DER MADE	Shell Global Solutions International B.V.
Barend	VERACHTERT	European Commission
Walter	VERMEIREN	TOTAL Petrochemicals R&D Belgium
Tatiana	VILARINHO	CEA-Liten
Sara	VINKLATOVA	Leitat Technological Center
Bert	WECKHUYSEN	Utrecht University
Helge	WESSEL	European Commission
Michael	WESSEL	Project Management Jülich
Malgorzata	WITKO	Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry PAS
Benjamin	WYNIGER	CEA/EERA

Main changes in the updated version :

Page 3 & 5. Final closing event, the SUNERGY kick-off, added to the executive summary and purpose paragraph.

Page 9. Figure 10 added, poster format of the outreach roll-up.

Page 14. Figure 17, new roadmap infographic added.

Page 16-18. Description and captures of the last videos released, added.

Page 19. Last newsletter and captures of the one-year wrap-up added.

Page 20-22. Point 3. Cooperation with Energy-X, joint materials point added.

Page 29-30. Last press release, 4th, added.

Page 31-42. Update of press clippings.

Page 50-51. Capture of the SUNERGY Kick-off agenda added.

Page 52-55. Capture of the SUNERGY Kick-off registration list added.

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